

**D3.3.2: Report on the
epidemiological survey
results and risk factor
assessment for pet human
SARS-Cov-2 transmission.
JIP COVRIN WP3**

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EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SURVEY DESIGN AND RISK FACTOR ASSESSMENT FOR PET HUMAN SARS-COV-2 TRANSMISSION

INTRODUCTION

COVRIN aims to integrate research by One Health EJP partner institutes on the topics of SARS-CoV-2 emergence, risk assessment and preparedness. The project has two main operational objectives: (i) to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2, and (ii) to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2. To achieve these objectives, integrative research activities are focused on four topics: (i) research on detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal species and the environment; (ii) research on SARS-CoV-2 molecular and biological characterization; (iii) SARS-CoV-2 surveillance and risk assessment, focussed on the animal human interface; and (iv) coronavirus preparedness. The overall aim of the COVRIN project is to generate and share data of these integrative research activities, in order to increase the preparedness for future coronavirus outbreaks.

1. Description of the task

WP3 aims to integrate the currently fragmented data from sampling of animals and the environment across partner countries, into an aligned One-Health surveillance system for SARS-CoV-2 that is based on data from the three components (i.e. humans, animals, and the environment), as well as the different sectors therein (e.g. pets, livestock, wildlife).

This report describes the outcomes of Subtask 3.3.2 “Identification of potential risk

factors for pet-human transmission of SARS-Cov-2” which is part of Task 3.3 “Risk factors for virus transmission” (WP3).

Many uncertainties about the behaviour of SARS-CoV-2 persist, and understanding all the keys of this epidemic requires an interdisciplinary One Health approach spanning the human and animal health sectors. The closest coexistence between people and animals occurs in large cities. This subtask aims to identify potential risk factors for pet-to-human transmission of SARS-CoV-2. To

achieve this goal, we analyzed samples of laboratory data from pets that have lived with family groups affected by SARS-CoV-2 in areas of high population density and high disease incidence. Our objective is to gain a better understanding of the factors that contribute to the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 between pets and humans, and ultimately, to develop strategies to prevent such transmission. Additionally, in this subtask a dashboard tool was developed. This tool, called SARS-BOARD, can be used to explore, in a dynamic and spatial way, outbreaks of SARS-CoV-2 in animals at a global level.

This tool provide valuable insights into the distribution and incidence of SARS-CoV-2 in animals, as well as the potential risk factors for transmission between different species.

Overall, this subtask represents an important step in the ongoing efforts to understand the impact of SARS-CoV-2 on both human and animal populations by **identifying, exploring and addressing the factors that contribute to the transmission of this virus.**

2. Description of the work and preliminary results

A conceptual assessment of the epidemiological survey and sampling design was carried out in a region of Spain with a high prevalence of SARS-Cov2 infection. In order to collect epidemiological and clinical data on family groups affected by the disease and their pets, a network of veterinary clinics has been created to provide sampling points for the pets. The SARS-Cov2 affected family groups include both hospital health workers and non-health workers pet owners in order to evaluate heavily and typically exposed pets (informed through the vet clinic network). The health workers recruited for this study are affiliated with two public hospitals that collaborated with our group through two national projects (EPICO and SANICOVID).

Each owner completed a consent form, an epidemiological questionnaire online or on paper, and a confidential health questionnaire. For each pet, these three documents, as well as samples (oral and nasal swabs and blood), are collected (described and available at Deliverable D3.3.1 "Report on the design of the epidemiological survey and clinical data" on the OHEJP page <https://onehealthjep.eu/groups/covrin/documents>)

Surveys were statistically analysed and samples were analysed by PCR and ELISA at the CISA (INIA-CSIC) laboratory. These results were analyzed to identify potential risk factors for SARS-CoV-2 transmission at the human-pet interface, and can be used to inform mathematical modelling and risk analysis

It is difficult to consult and explore global information regarding SARS-CoV2 in pets and other animals at real time. To overcome this difficulty, an easy-to-use tool called SARS-board was developed. This

open-source dashboard application allows to explore outbreaks, and also combine it climate and socioeconomic data. It presents this information on interactive maps that can be used to monitor the disease evolution in animals.

2.1. Sampling pets and diagnosis of infections with SARS-Cov-2 using PCR-ELISA :

Incorporating a more specific ELISA test (ID-VET: DOUBLE ANTIGEN MULTI-SPECIES ELISA) produced new results, increasing the proportion of positive SARS-Cov-2 PCR-ELISA results in dog samples.

The preliminary study was completed, and the epidemiological survey and sampling protocols were shared with other partners/countries in the Deliverable 3.3.1 report. In a second stage, we collaborated with Universidad Alfonso X El Sabio (UAX), which conducted testing for SARS-CoV-2 in pets of infected owners and administered a similar epidemiological survey. This other group has conducted tests on pets that belonged to SARS-Cov2-infected owners and found a comparable percentage of positive results. We are standardizing the epidemiological information that is provided to pet owners in order to increase the number of animals that participate in the survey's collection of epidemiological data in the same region. As a result, the number of dog samples increased by 41. The combined results are included in this report.

All pets were negative for SARS-CoV-2, but IgM or/and IgG α -SARS-CoV-2 were detected in 5/18 cats (27.8%) and 21/69 dogs (30.4%), with α -CCoV detected in 13/20 dogs.

Seroprevalence in dogs (29,5%) is consistent with other authors' findings in dogs from Spain, France, and other severely affected areas.

Seroprevalence in cats (23,81%) is consistent with other authors' findings in cats from Italy, Brazil, France, and other severely affected areas.

The findings will allow for the identification of potential risk factors for the transmission of SARS-Cov-2 in the human-pet interface, which can be used to feed mathematical modelling and risk analysis, Currently, the article detailing all of the findings of this section and the next is being written.

2.2 Study of the epidemiology and risk factors in pets

The epidemiological investigation included 87 pets, comprising 18 cats (7 males and 9 females, aged 1-18 years) and 69 dogs (20 males and 41 females, aged 1-15 years), with 31/87 from households of health workers.

The results of the epidemiology and risk factor study in pets have shown that close contact with SARS-CoV-2 positive owners does not appear to be a determining factor for a higher humoral immune response to SARS-CoV-2 in pets.

In most of the cat surveys, owners shared bedrooms and beds, including four out of the five cats that tested positive for antibodies. Of the five cats that tested positive for coronavirus antibodies, three developed digestive symptoms. The positive cat breeds were three European common shorthairs, one Birman, and one Siamese.

Several dogs with SARS-CoV-2 antibodies developed digestive and/or respiratory symptoms (8 out of 21). In dogs, sex (12/36 female and 6/16 males), body condition, and age did not show significant differences between dogs with and without antibodies. In the majority of dog surveys (76%), dogs lived and slept inside the house, including 85% of the dogs that tested positive for antibodies. Out of the 21 dogs that tested positive for coronavirus antibodies, 10 (47%) developed symptoms: 40% had respiratory symptoms and 60% had digestive symptoms.

Although there is currently no evidence of dogs or cats playing a role in the spread of COVID-19, this study aims to expand our understanding of the epidemiology and evolution of the disease in pets. Owners' behavior during their infectious period, such as sharing bedding with pets, could pose a higher risk of infection for pets.

Ongoing statistical analysis will be included in the final version of this deliverable D3.3.2 report.

A manuscript is currently being finalized that includes the epidemiological study and laboratory results on the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in pets. The results have been submitted to the International Conference on Livestock, Companion Animals and Wildlife Coronaviruses (25-26th May 2023).

2.3.) Development of a dashboard to explore outbreaks of SARS-CoV2 in animals

It is difficult to consult and explore global information regarding SARS-CoV2 in pets and other animals at real time. To overcome this difficulty, an easy-to-use tool called **SARS-board** was developed. This open-source dashboard application allows to explore SARS-CoV2 outbreaks in animals (including pets, wildlife and other animals), and also combine it climate and socioeconomic data. It presents this information on interactive maps that can be used to monitor the disease evolution in animals.

SARS-board contains 3 tabs, displays, or sections which integrates SARS-CoV-2 outbreak data (WOAH, formerly OIE), temperature data (Climate Data Online) and socioeconomic factors (World

Bank Data) and includes options to change the base map in order to explore outbreaks combining with roads, topographic data etc, as well as a timeline to select outbreaks worldwide in animals in a specific time period since 2020.

SARS-board

The SARS-board tool app is available on the INIA website (<https://www.inia.es/serviciosyrecursos/recursosdocumentales/visor%20de%20SARS-Cov2%20en%20animales/Paginas/Home.aspx>)

The screenshot shows the INIA website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with options like 'EDITORIAL', 'ACCESO CONVOCATORIAS', 'INTRANET', 'SEDE ELECTRÓNICA', 'TRANSFERENCIA TECNOLÓGICA', 'DIRECTORIO', 'ES', and 'Buscador'. Below the menu, there is a header with the INIA logo and a search bar. The main content area is titled 'SERVICIOS Y RECURSOS > RECURSOS DOCUMENTALES' and features a large heading 'Visor de SARS-Cov2 en animales'. Below the heading, there is a description: 'SARS-Board es una herramienta interactiva para explorar los brotes de SARS-Cov2 en animales. Permite relacionarlo con factores socioeconómicos y climáticos, así como visualizar y seleccionar los brotes por especies, zonas o periodos concretos.' To the right of the description, there is a button labeled 'ABRIR VISOR' and a link 'Visor de SARS-Cov2 en animales'. On the left side of the page, there is a sidebar with a list of links: 'SERVICIOS Y RECURSOS', 'RECURSOS DOCUMENTALES', 'Visor de SARS-Cov2 en animales', 'Biblioteca y Documentación', 'Forestales', 'Vegetales', 'Visor comparativo de contenidos de carbono', 'Visor comparativo de especies forestales', and 'Visor de SARS-Cov2 en animales'. The bottom part of the page shows a preview of the SARS-board tool interface, which is the same as the one shown in the previous figure.

on the MATRIX project platform for Practical Examples of Dashboards and Tools (<https://svase.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/examples/#practical-examples-of-dashboards-and-tools>).

Data are routinely collected from different data sources, including,

1. SARS-CoV2 outbreaks information retrieved from WOAHI; data for each outbreak include country, administrative unit, coordinates (latitude and longitude), date of occurrence and confirmation of the event, species, number of cases, deaths, destroyed and slaughtered animals.
2. Temperature (°F) and Wind speed (km/h) at real time
3. Socioeconomical factors from World Bank Data.

SARS-board tools combine several geographical analytical tools implementing through Python, JavaScript and ArcGIS scripts. Temperature and world bank socioeconomical data are included as permanent layers in a web map application and outbreaks data are updated weekly as a feature layer. The visitor web dashboard for the data exploration uses the geoweb services provided by the ArcGIS server Enterprise. ArcGIS Server spreads the ArcGIS Pro project and its layers in the form of ReST web services.

The SARS-board contains 3 tabs, displays, or sections, specifically:

- 1)The historical outbreak records tab is the main page for exploring and visualizing data. This section includes to the top a map of SARS-CoV2 outbreaks from 2020 to the present, a time slider of outbreak notifications at the bottom, and a list of interactive graphics on the right related to the region of the total

or selection of outbreaks that we could develop in the map or in the time graphic. The time slider tool enables users to wind back the time and view the global situation on any given moment of the outbreaks since 2020 as well as to select time periods by species and regions. By clicking on any outbreak, a pop-up window with the outbreak information appears.

The outbreaks are classified into four types of animals:

- 1) Captive: These are wild animals that are housed in captivity, such as zoo animals, but whose phenotypes are unaffected by human selection.
- 2) Domestic: This category includes livestock and farm animals, including those raised for fur production.
- 3) Wild: This refers to animals whose phenotypes are unaffected by human selection and that live independently of direct human supervision or control. This category also includes feral animals, which are animals of domesticated species that now live without direct human supervision or control.
- 4) Pets: These are animals that live under direct human supervision or control, typically for companionship, and include dogs, cats, rabbits, and other similar animals.

2)The tab "Country data," country-level information from World Bank Data (<https://www.worldbank.org/en/home>) on:

- Population per square kilometer
- CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita)
- CO2 emissions (kt)
- Consumer price index
- Coverage of social safety net programs
- PM2.5 air pollution

Additionally, it provides real-time climate information from the National Centers for Environmental Information (<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/cdo-web>):

- Air temperature (°F)
- Wind speed (km/h)

3)The tab " World globe " allows users to explore SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks notifications in animals at the entire globe including a search place tool.

3. Bibliography

- Hosie, M. J., Hofmann-Lehmann, R., Hartmann, K., Egberink, H., Truyen, U., Addie, D. D., ... & Möstl, K. (2021). Anthropogenic infection of cats during the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic. *Viruses*, 13(2), 185.
- Schulz C. et al., (2021) SARS-CoV-2-specific antibodies in domestic cats during first COVID-19 wave, Europe. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2712.211252>, https://wwwnc.cdc.gov/eid/article/27/12/21-1252_article
- *Guidelines for Working with Free-Ranging Wild Mammals in the Era of the COVID-19 Pandemic. OIE*
- Decaro, N., & Buonavoglia, C. (2008). An update on canine coronaviruses: viral evolution and pathobiology. *Veterinary microbiology*, 132(3-4), 221-234.
- Greger, M. (2007). The human/animal interface: emergence and resurgence of zoonotic infectious diseases. *Critical reviews in microbiology*, 33(4), 243-299.
- Bosco-Lauth, A. M., Hartwig, A. E., Porter, S. M., Gordy, P. W., Nehring, M., Byas, A. D., ... & Bowen, R. A. (2020). Pathogenesis, transmission and response to re-exposure of SARS-CoV-2 in domestic cats. *BioRxiv*.

- *Preventative Measures regarding SARS-CoV-2 and Ferrets in the UK December 2020*. APHA
- Hammer, A. S., Quaade, M. L., Rasmussen, T. B., Fonager, J., Rasmussen, M., Mundbjerg, K., ... & Bøtner, A. (2021). SARS-CoV-2 transmission between mink (*Neovison vison*) and humans, Denmark. *Emerging infectious diseases*, 27(2), 547.
- E.I. Patterson, G. Elia, A. Grassi, A. Giordano, C. Desario, M. Medardo, S.L. Smith, E.R. Anderson, T. Prince, G.T. Patterson, E. Lorusso, M.S. Lucente, G. Lanave, S. Lauzi, U. Bonfanti, A. Stranieri, V. Martella, F. Solarì Basano, V.R. Barrs, A.D. Radford, U. Agrimi, G. L. Hughes, S. Paltrinieri, N. Decaro *bioRxiv* 2020.07.21.214346; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.07.21.214346>
- Shi, J., Wen, Z., Zhong, G., Yang, H., Wang, C., Huang, B., ... & Bu, Z. (2020). Susceptibility of ferrets, cats, dogs, and other domesticated animals to SARS–coronavirus 2. *Science*, 368(6494), 1016-1020.
- SARS-CoV-2 neutralizing serum antibodies in cats: a serological investigation, Qiang Zhang, Huajun Zhang, Kun Huang, Yong Yang, Xianfeng Hui, Jindong Gao, Xinglin He, Chengfei Li, Wenxiao Gong, Yufei Zhang, Cheng Peng, Xiaoxiao Gao, Huanchun Chen, Zhong Zou, Zhengli Shi, Meilin Jin *bioRxiv* 2020.04.01.021196; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.04.01.021196>
- Boklund, A.; Hammer, A.S.; Quaade, M.L.; Rasmussen, T.B.; Lohse, L.; Strandbygaard, B.; Jørgensen, C.S.; Olesen, A.S.; Hjerpe, F.B.; Petersen, H.H.; Jensen, T.K.; et al. SARS-CoV-2 in Danish Mink Farms: Course of the Epidemic and a Descriptive Analysis of the Outbreaks in 2020. *Animals* 2021, 11, 164. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11010164>
- Dhama, K., Khan, S., Tiwari, R., Sircar, S., Bhat, S., Malik, Y. S., ... & Rodríguez-Morales, A. J. (2020). Coronavirus disease 2019–COVID-19. *Clinical microbiology reviews*, 33(4), e00028-20.
- *Relation between the biodiversity crisis and emerging infectious diseases, such as Covid-19*. European Commission
- Garigliany, M., Van Laere, A. S., Clercx, C., Giet, D., Escriou, N., Huon, C., ... & Desmecht, D. (2020). SARS-CoV-2 natural transmission from human to cat, Belgium, March 2020. *Emerging infectious diseases*, 26(12), 3069.
- 20.OIE. A_Factsheet_SARS-CoV-2
- Ruiz-Arrondo, I., Portillo, A., Palomar, A. M., Santibáñez, S., Santibáñez, P., Cervera, C., & Oteo, J. A. (2021). Detection of SARS-CoV-2 in pets living with COVID-19 owners diagnosed during the COVID-19 lockdown in Spain: A case of an asymptomatic cat with SARS-CoV-2 in Europe. *Transboundary and emerging diseases*, 68(2), 973-976.
- Segalés, J., Puig, M., Rodon, J., Avila-Nieto, C., Carrillo, J., Cantero, G., ... & Vergara-Alert, J. (2020). Detection of SARS-CoV-2 in a cat owned by a COVID-19– affected patient in Spain. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(40), 24790-24793.
- Tiwari, R., Dhama, K., Sharun, K., Iqbal Yattoo, M., Malik, Y. S., Singh, R., ... & Rodríguez-Morales, A. J. (2020). COVID-19: animals, veterinary and zoonotic links. *Veterinary Quarterly*, 40(1), 169-182.
- Barrs, V. R., Peiris, M., Tam, K. W., Law, P. Y., Brackman, C. J., To, E. M., ... & Sit, T. H. (2020). SARS-CoV-2 in quarantined domestic cats from COVID-19 households or close contacts, Hong Kong, China. *Emerging infectious diseases*, 26(12), 3071.
- Lorenzo, D., & Carrisi, C. (2020). COVID-19 exposure risk for family members of healthcare workers: An observational study. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 98, 287-289.
- Fernández-de-Mera, I. G., Rodríguez del-Río, F. J., de la Fuente, J., Pérez-Sancho, M., Hervás, D., Moreno, I., ... & Gortázar, C. (2021). Detection of environmental SARS-CoV-2 RNA in a high prevalence setting in Spain. *Transboundary and emerging diseases*, 68(3), 1487-1492.
- Bosco-Lauth, A. M., Hartwig, A. E., Porter, S. M., Gordy, P. W., Nehring, M., Byas, A. D., ... & Bowen, R. A. (2020). Pathogenesis, transmission and response to re-exposure of SARS-CoV-2 in domestic cats. *BioRxiv*.
- McAloose, D., Laverack, M., Wang, L., Killian, M. L., Caserta, L. C., Yuan, F., ... & Diel, D. G. (2020). From people to Panthera: Natural SARS-CoV-2 infection in tigers and lions at the Bronx Zoo. *MBio*, 11(5), e02220-20.
- Gortázar, C., Barroso-Arévalo, S., Ferreras-Colino, E., Isla, J., de la Fuente, G., Rivera, B., ... & Sánchez-Vizcaíno, J. M. (2021). Natural SARS-CoV-2 infection in kept ferrets, Spain. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 27(7), 1994.
- Aguiló-Gisbert, J., Padilla-Blanco, M., Lizana, V., Maiques, E., Muñoz-Baquero, M., Chillida-Martínez, E., ... & Rubio-Guerri, C. (2021). First description of SARS-CoV-2 infection in two feral American mink (*Neovison vison*) caught in the wild. *Animals*, 11(5), 1422.
- Martínez-Cortés, M., León-Dominguez, C. M., Fernandez-Pinero, J., Rodriguez, M., Almonacid, M., Ferrari, M. J., ... & Pollán, M. (2022). SARS-CoV-2 surveillance strategy in essential workers of the Madrid City Council during the first epidemic wave in Spain, March–July 2020. *Occupational and environmental medicine*, 79(5), 295-303.

- Miró, G., Regidor-Cerrillo, J., Checa, R., Diezma-Díaz, C., Montoya, A., García-Cantalejo, J., ... & Ortega-Mora, L. M. (2021). SARS-CoV-2 infection in one cat and three dogs living in COVID-19-positive households in Madrid, Spain. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 1292.
- Palmer, M. V., Martins, M., Falkenberg, S., Buckley, A., Caserta, L. C., Mitchell, P. K., ... & Diel, D. G. (2021). Susceptibility of white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) to SARS-CoV-2. *Journal of virology*, 95(11), e00083-21.
- Barroso-Arévalo, S., Barneto, A., Ramos, Á. M., Rivera, B., Sánchez, R., Sánchez-Morales, L., ... & Sánchez-Vizcaíno, J. M. (2021). Large-scale study on virological and serological prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 in cats and dogs in Spain. *Transboundary and emerging diseases*.
- Hosie, M. J., Hofmann-Lehmann, R., Hartmann, K., Egberink, H., Truyen, U., Addie, D. D., ... & Möstl, K. (2021). Anthropogenic infection of cats during the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic. *Viruses*, 13(2), 185.
- Munnink, B. B. O., Sikkema, R. S., Nieuwenhuijse, D. F., Molenaar, R. J., Munger, E., Molenkamp, R., ... & Koopmans, M. P. (2020). Jumping back and forth: anthroozoonotic and zoonotic transmission of SARS-CoV-2 on mink farms. *BioRxiv*.
- Exposure of humans or animals to sArs-cov-2 from wild, livestock, companion and aquatic animals Qualitative exposure assessment. FAOM.E. Halloran et al., *Design and Analysis of Vaccine Studies, Statistics for Biology and Health*, DOI 10.1007/978-0-387-68636-310, 205cSpringer Science+Business Media, LLC 2010
- Rostami A, Sepidarkish M, Leeflang MMG, Riahi SM, Nourollahpour Shiadeh M, Esfandyari S, Mokdad AH, Hotez PJ, Gasser RB. SARS-CoV-2 seroprevalence worldwide: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Microbiol Infect*. 2021 Mar;27(3):331-340. doi: 10.1016/j.cmi.2020.10.020. Epub 2020 Oct 24. PMID: 33228974; PMCID: PMC7584920.